

THE ROLE OF GENERAL FITNESS AT THE INITIAL STAGE TAEKWANDO TRAINING

Gofurov Sherali

Abdufattoyev Abror

Uzbek state university of physical education and sport

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Abstract. Taekwondo is a national ancient Korean martial art that successfully combines the ancient principles and methods of training with the trends of modern sports, is a unique system of self-development and physical education, and is also a spectacular and dynamic sport. " Taekwondo " is one of the youngest, rapidly developing types of martial arts, which has gained recognition in more than 200 countries around the world. "Taekwondo - a unified version that combines the technique of nine schools, means in translation: the path of the hand and foot (leg and fist). How an Olympic sport is a scientifically based way of using one's physical abilities for the purpose of self-defense (1,2,4,5)

Keywords: Taekwondo , martial arts, self-defense, martial art, side kick (dolio chagi).

РОЛЬ ОБЩЕЙ ФИТНЕС НА НАЧАЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ ТРЕНИРОВКИ ТХЭКВАНДО

Аннотация. Тхэквондо – национальное древнекорейское боевое искусство, удачно сочетающее древние принципы и методы тренировок с тенденциями современного спорта, представляет собой уникальную систему саморазвития и физического воспитания, а также является зрелищным и динамичным видом спорта. «Тхэквондо» — один из самых молодых, бурно развивающихся видов единоборств, получивший признание более чем в 200 странах мира. «Тхэквондо — унифицированный вариант, объединяющий технику девяти школ, в переводе означает: путь руки и ноги (ноги и кулака). Как олимпийский вид спорта является научно обоснованным способом использования своих физических возможностей в целях самообороны (1,2,4,5)

Ключевые слова: тхэквондо, боевые искусства, самооборона, боевое искусство, боковой удар (долио чаги).

Introduction. Thanks to this sport, as a result of intensive physical and spiritual training, a person can reveal his hidden individual capabilities. Taekwondo classes serve as an effective means of physical and moral improvement, harmonious development of personality, as well as the formation of a person's internal culture, his character and strong-willed qualities, which allows an athlete to have a high level of responsibility and self-control (3 , 6).

The purpose of this work is to analyze the basics of physical development at the initial stage of training in Taekwondo .

The main objectives of the study include:

- study of methodological and organizational features of Taekwondo as a martial art in the system of physical education;
- development and testing of complexes of physical exercises that develop speed qualities in Taekwondo among boys 12-14 years old.

- **Research methods.**

Of the main research methods, it is necessary to highlight:

- theoretical analysis and generalization of data scientific literature;
- specialized websites;
- networks "Internet";
- normative documents;
- competition protocols ;
- testing;
- pedagogical experiment; - methods of mathematical statistics.
- **Organization of the study.**

The study was conducted in three stages on the basis of the state institution "Asenkritovskaya secondary school of the NGO Akimat of the Taranovo district" for 6 months.

The first stage is theoretical: the general direction of the study was determined, a general hypothesis was studied and formed, primary materials were accumulated for subsequent analysis and generalization, a survey of children aged 12-14 was conducted in order to determine the initial level of their physical fitness.

The second stage - a pedagogical experiment - the main method of a specially organized study was carried out in order to determine the effectiveness of the use of various means and methods for the development of the conditioning abilities of athletes. Since the object of this work is the mechanisms and tools for influencing physical development during taekwondo classes , the second stage included a study in 2 parts. (6,11,16,22,40,41)

In the first part of the 2nd stage, a pedagogical study was carried out, the basis of which was the developed experimental training program. The experiment involved 20 people of the same age (12-14 years old), with the same level of sports qualification.

2 groups were organized: control and experimental, 10 people each.

Classes were held:

in the control group: Monday - Wednesday - Friday from 19.00 to 20.30;

in the experimental group:

Tuesday - Thursday - Saturday from 19.00 to 20.30.

In accordance with the purpose and objectives of the work, the training process of the experimental group included sets of exercises based on the methodology of E.N. Zakharov , modified to meet the requirements of shock training in taekwondo . The group followed the traditional method. (3,12,18,25,30,34)

Testing.

It was carried out in two stages, the venue of the State Institution "Asenkritovskaya secondary school of the education department of the akimat of the Taranovsky district."

Time in the control group: Wednesday - 16:00, in the experimental group Wednesday - 17.00.

Tests to determine the frequency of movements of the arms and legs.

1. Test – "direct blow with the right / left hand in 10 seconds."

Testing procedure: the subject performs direct blows with his hands (right and left), to the shield for 10 seconds, stops at the signal. performance.

Equipment: shield, whistle, stopwatch.

2. Test – “running in place for 10 seconds.”

Testing procedure: the subject runs in place, alternately touching the cord with his knees for 10 seconds, stops running on a signal.

Equipment: cord, stopwatch, whistle.

3. Test – “kick with the right / left foot in 10 seconds.”

Test procedure: Subject performs side kick

(dolio chagi) with the right and left foot in the paws for 10 seconds, stops the execution on a signal.

Equipment: projectile, whistle, stopwatch. Tests for measuring speed -strength abilities (Lyakh V. I, 1998).

4. Flexion - extension of the arms in support for 20 seconds.

Testing procedure: the subject performs the bending of the arms in support for 20 seconds, the angle of flexion is 90 degrees. Stops execution on a signal. *Equipment:* whistle, stopwatch.

Table 1

A set of exercises based on the methodology of E.N. Zakharova (stage 1)

Tests		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Arm curl	end №4	30	25	21	31	34	22	33	25	29	33
in emphasis for 20 s., number of times											
	Start	28	23	19	29	29	20	29	23	25	33
squat for 20 e., number of times	end	22	23	21	21	22	20	21	20	19	21
	Start	21	21	21	21	23	22	20	19	21	20
Leg frequency (pr.n. , lv.n.) in 10 s. number of times	end	17	19	16	16	19	19	17	19	18	18
	Start	17	17	14	15	18	18	17	19	18	18
	end start	20	21	17	19	17	20	19	19	18	19
	Start	19	19	17	14	17	20	16	19	17	19
Running in place for 10 e., number of times	end №. 2	40	41	36	37	39	36	40	39	32	33
	Start	36	37	34	33	36	35	37	39	29	33
Frequency movements hands, number of times	end	38	38	36	39	30	40	29	30	31	26

	Start	36	44	30	39	28	38	27	25	30	24
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After the first part of the 2nd stage of the study, there was a second test, control exercises were performed in the same sequence and according to the same regulations.

table 2

A set of exercises based on the methodology of E.N. Zakharova (stage 2)

Tests		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Arm curl in emphasis for 20 s., number of times	end	30	25	21	31	34	22	33	25	29	33
	No. 4										
Squat for 20 e., number of times	Start	28	23	19	29	29	20	29	23	25	33
	end	22	23	21	21	22	20	21	20	19	21
Leg frequency (pr.n. , lv.n.) in 10 s. number of times	Start	21	21	21	21	23	22	20	19	21	20
	end	17	19	16	16	19	19	17	19	18	18
	Start	17	17	14	15	18	18	17	19	18	18
	end start	20	21	17	19	17	20	19	19	18	19
Running in place for 10 e., number of times	Start	19	19	17	14	17	20	16	19	17	19
	end No. 2	40	41	36	37	39	36	40	39	32	33
Frequency hand movements , number of times	Start	36	37	34	33	36	35	37	39	29	33
	end	38	38	36	39	30	40	29	30	31	26
	Start	36	44	30	39	28	38	27	25	30	24

The third stage was devoted to the analytical generalization of the obtained experimental data, the final generalization of the materials of the entire study, and the completion of the preparation of the text of the work.

Summary

Based on the studied scientific and methodological literature on the development of human speed abilities, based on the methodology of E.N. Zakharov, we have developed sets of exercises aimed at educating speed qualities in 12-14 year old boys involved in taekwondo

The developed complexes were planned included in the training process and tested for 3 months in the classes of elementary training groups of the 3rd year of study of the taekwondo department .

The effectiveness of the developed complexes is confirmed by the results obtained during repeated testing.

A significant increase in speed indicators among young men aged 12-14 in the experimental group involved in taekwondo indicates the effectiveness of the improved methodology.

REFERENCES.

1. Захаров Е.Н., Карасев А.В., Сафронов А.А. Энциклопедия физической подготовки (Методические основы развития физических качеств) под об. редак. А.В. Карасев. - М., Лептос, 2010 - 368с
2. Иванков Ч.Т. Исследование системы " двух борцов" с позиции биомеханики ударных действий в Таэквондо.
3. / Ч.Т. Иванков, И.С. Зенченко// Материалы докладов Н-М конференции. Выпуск. 5М.: МГПУПИФК, 2006, - С.21-23
4. Лигай В.Таэквондо- путь к совершенству/ В. Лигай. - Ташкент: Шарк, 1994. 160с
5. Макаров Н. психологическая самоподготовка к рукопашному бою: Учебное пособие / Н.Макаров, Г.Антонов- Мн.: ЧП С. Ананич, ПКФ" Издательский дом" , 1993.-80с
6. Подпалько С.П. Биомеханизмы ударных технических действий в Таэквондо. ВТФ/
7. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5Х5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
8. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
9. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
10. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
11. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.

12. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01. 2022).
13. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR MAKTABLARIDA SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
14. Еофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA ROG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.
15. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШЕУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
16. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.
17. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.
18. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02. 2022).
19. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
20. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
21. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor O. G., Li Baxtiyorov U. A. S. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
22. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

23. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETES IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.
24. ҒОҒУРОВ Ш. Х. БОЛАЛАР ВА ЎСМИРЛАР СПОРТ МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНҒИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУҲИДА ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //Фан-Спортга. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
25. Sherali Xoshimovich G’Ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G’Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG’ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 09.01.2023).
26. Gofurov, S. X., Berdiyeva, C. A., Berdiyev, S. D., & Atabayev, A. N. (2022). A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(12), 179-189.
27. Hoshimovich, G. S., Hoshimovich, G. B., & Ibragim o’g’li, K. S. (2022). Differentiated Approach to Improving the Physical Qualities of Students With Disabilities. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 15, 213-223.
28. Sherali Hoshimovich G’Ofurov QISQA MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHI SPORTCHILARNI MASHG’ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 09.01.2023).
29. Sherali Hoshimovich G’Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O’G’Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL АТЛЕТИКА MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG’ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
30. Sherali Hoshimovich G’Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG’ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
31. Sherali Hoshimovich G’Ofurov QISQA MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHI SPORTCHILARNI MASHG’ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).

32. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugafarovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSH DAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
33. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.
34. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETES IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.
35. Hoshimovich G. S. et al. Differentiated Approach to Improving the Physical Qualities of Students With Disabilities //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 15. – С. 213-223.
36. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5x5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
37. Gofurov S. SPECIALIZES IN ORGANIZING ATHLETIC EXERCISE GROUPS APPLICATION OF EXERCISES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 659-662.
38. Khoshimovich G. S. Rowing With the Help of Special Equipment and Methods of Balance Development in Canoeing //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 26-30.
39. Gofurov S. H., Tashpolatova K. G., Ollaberganov S. E. University Students Methods of Preparation for Sport of Powerlifting //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 31-35.
40. Teacher, Gafurov Sherali Khoshimovich. "ROWING WITH THE HELP OF SPECIAL EQUIPMENT AND METHODS OF BALANCE DEVELOPMENT IN CANOEING." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.1 (2023).
41. Makhammadjonovich, Giyasov Temur, Gofurov Sherali Hoshimovich, and Palvanov Avazkhan Abdullaevich. "PHYSICAL FITNESS OF LONG JUMPER 14-15 YEAR OLD ATHLETES ENGAGED IN TRAINING GROUP INCREASING EFFICIENCY." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 1.1 (2022).

42. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев, Рухиддин Фахриддинович Одилов, Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Н. Ш. Бобомуродов ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/imkoniyati-cheklangan-engil-atletikachi-ulo-tiruvchilarning-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
43. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Sherzod Abdurahmonovich Abdiyev, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Azizbek Xoshimjon O'G'Li Uzoqov ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН БОЛАЛАР НАЙОТИДА АДАПТИВИЙ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯНИНГ О'РНИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/imkoniyati-cheklangan-bolalar-hayotida-adaptiviy-jismoniy-tarbiyaning-o-rni> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
44. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR АРАВАЧАСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНАДИГАН УМУРТҚА ПОГ'ОНАСИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН YOSHLARNING АДАПТИВ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯСИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).